

N-Substituted Phenothiazines as Redox Indicators in Cerimetry

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Promethazine hydrochloride, prochlorperazine maleate, butaperazine dimaleate and trifluoperazine dihydrochloride are proposed as redox indicators in the cerimetric titration of iron(II), molybdenum(V), uranium(IV), hydroquinone, metol and ascorbic acid in sulphuric, hydrochloric and acetic acid media. They give sharp and reversible colour change at the equivalence point. They have certain advantages over the existing redox indicators in cerimetry. Their transition potentials are reported.

N-SUBSTITUTED phenothiazines were proposed as redox indicators in titrations with sodium vanadate¹⁻⁴, cerium(IV) sulphate⁵⁻⁷, potassium bromate⁸, chloramine-T⁹, chloramine-B¹⁰ and N-bromosuccinimide¹¹. In the present communication the authors have carried out detailed investigations on the indicator properties of promethazine hydrochloride (PH), prochlorperazine maleate (PCPM), butaperazine dimaleate (BPDM) and trifluoperazine dihydrochloride (TFP) in cerimetric titrations of iron(II), molybdenum(V), uranium(IV), hydroquinone, metol and ascorbic acid.

Experimental

Reagents: Aqueous solutions (0.1% m/V) of PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP were prepared and stored in amber bottles. BPDM and PCPM were prepared in hot water.

Approximately 0.1N solutions of iron(II), molybdenum(V), uranium(IV), hydroquinone, metol and ascorbic acid were prepared and standardised by the accepted methods. Other working solutions were made by suitable dilution of these solutions. All reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

Apparatus: The potentiometric assembly consisted of a direct reading potentiometer, a mirror galvanometer, a bright platinum gauze indicator electrode, a saturated calomel reference electrode and an agar salt bridge. The titration mixture was stirred by a magnetic stirrer.

Determination of transition potentials: The transition potentials of PH, BPDM, TFP and PCPM in the titration of iron(II) with cerium(IV) sulphate were determined by the potentiometric method¹.

Cerimetric titration of iron(II), uranium(IV), molybdenum(V), hydroquinone, metol and ascorbic acid: 20 ml of 0.05-0.01N iron(II), molybdenum(V), hydroquinone or metol, 1 ml of 0.1% PH, PCPM, BPDM or TFP (2 ml of 0.1% PCPM or BPDM for hydroquinone and no PCPM for metol) indicator and 3 ml of 10M phosphoric acid were diluted to 40 ml with acid to give 0.75M sulphuric acid or 1M hydrochloric acid or acetic acid at the end-point

(0.5M HCl for hydroquinone and 0.3M HCl for metol). The mixture was titrated with 0.05-0.01N cerium(IV) sulphate solution to the appearance of a pink or orange-red colour.

20 ml of 0.05-0.01N uranium(IV) solution, 1 ml of 0.1% PH or BPDM, 20 ml of 5M sulphuric acid and 3 ml of 10M phosphoric acid were diluted to 100 ml with water. The solution was titrated with 0.05-0.01N cerium(IV) sulphate.

In the titration of 0.1-0.05N ascorbic acid, 20 ml of ascorbic acid and 2 ml of 10M phosphoric acid were diluted to 40 ml with acid to give a concentration of 1M hydrochloric acid or acetic acid at the end-point. The solution was titrated with cerium(IV) sulphate using 1 ml of 0.1% PH, PCPM, BPDM or TFP in the beginning in acetic acid medium and near the end-point in hydrochloric acid medium. Ascorbic acid was titrated in 0.3M sulphuric acid solution using 2 ml of 0.1% PCPM in the beginning and PH, BPDM or TFP near the end-point. Ascorbic acid was titrated with 0.10-0.005N cerium(IV) sulphate in 2M phosphoric acid in the presence of 1 ml of 0.1% PH, PCPM, BPDM or TFP indicator. In the titration of ascorbic acid in 2M phosphoric acid (15 ml) with 0.002N cerium(IV) sulphate only PCPM indicator functions.

Ascorbic acid in vitamin 'C' tablets and injections: An exact amount of well powdered vitamin 'C' tablets containing about 300 mg of ascorbic acid was dissolved in doubly distilled water. The solution was filtered to a 100 ml volumetric flask. For the assay of vitamin 'C' injection solution a known volume of the injection solution was diluted to 100 ml with doubly distilled water to give a concentration of 3 mg/ml of ascorbic acid. 10 ml of the above solution, 15 ml of 4M acetic acid or 5M phosphoric acid and 2 ml of 0.1% PH, PCPM, BPDM or TFP indicator solution were titrated with 0.05N cerium(IV) sulphate to the appearance of a pink or orange-red colour.

Ascorbic acid in citrus fruit juices: An aliquot of the extracted juice, 1 ml of 0.1% PH, PCPM,

BPDM or TFP and 1 drop of ethanol were diluted to 25 ml with phosphoric acid to give 3M at the end-point. The mixture was titrated with 0.005N cerium(IV) sulphate solution to the appearance of a pink colour.

Results and Discussion

PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP are highly soluble in water giving colourless solutions. BPDM gives a light yellow solution. The oxidation potentials⁸, molar absorptivities⁹ and probable mechanism of oxidation of the indicators^{8,9,11} have been reported. The transition potentials of PH, BPDM and TFP in the titration of iron(II) with cerium(IV) sulphate (Table 1) decrease with increasing

and higher concentration of sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acids. Premature end-points are observed in higher concentrations of phosphoric acid and acetic acids. The stability of the end-point colour of PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP is 48, 12, 4 and 4 hr respectively in sulphuric acid or hydrochloric acid and 3 hr in acetic acid medium (12 hr for PCPM).

It was found that 0.8-2 ml of 0.1% PH, PCPM, BPDM or TFP is necessary in a total volume of 60 ml for proper indicator action. Higher concentration of the indicator gives higher titre values.

The indicator correction needed for PH, PCPM, BPDM or TFP has been found by comparing the results from the potentiometric titration with those when the indicators were used. The average indicator correction is 0.03 ml of 0.01N cerium(IV) sulphate for 1 ml of 0.1% indicator solution.

Experiments have shown that tin(IV) chloride and mercury(I) and (II) chlorides do not interfere with the function of PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP indicators in the titration of iron(II). The indicators can therefore be usefully employed in the determination of iron(III) present in ferric alum and iron ores like haematite after the conventional method of reduction of iron(III) by tin(II) chloride.

All four indicators are superior to ferroin, the most widely used indicator in cerimetry in that they are more sensitive requiring less indicator correction and function in acetic acid medium. For this titration PH is recommended as the most sensitive indicator.

Titration of 0.1-0.01N molybdenum(V) solution : PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP give pleasing end-points from colourless to pink or orange-red in 0.2-1M sulphuric acid, 1-2M hydrochloric acid or 0.2-3M acetic acid medium containing 1-3 ml of 10M phosphoric acid in a total volume of 60 ml. Higher concentrations of sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid and acetic acids and a lower concentration of phosphoric acid give sluggish end-points. Higher acidities of phosphoric acid cause premature end-points. The stability of the end-point colour of the indicators decreases with an increase in acidity. Thus the stabilities of the end-point colour of PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP are 25-15, 120-15, 40-3 and 25-15 min in sulphuric acid; 25-20, 120-60, 35-15 and 35-30 min in hydrochloric acid and 35-30, 20-15, 20-15 and 45-15 min in acetic acid medium respectively.

A 0.8-2 ml of 0.1% of PH, PCPM, BPDM or TFP is required for proper indicator action in a total volume of 60 ml. The indicator correction needed for the indicators has been found by comparing the results from the potentiometric titration with those when the indicators were used. The average indicator correction is 0.04 ml of 0.01N cerium(IV) sulphate for 1 ml of 0.1% PH, PCPM, BPDM or TFP solution. PH provides the best sensitivity in this titration.

All four indicators are superior to ferroin because (i) they give sharper end-points in acetic

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF TRANSITION POTENTIALS OF PH, BPDM AND TFP IN THE TITRATION OF IRON(II) WITH CERIU(IV) SULPHATE

Sulphuric acid (M)	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.75
Indicator	Transition potentials (mV*)				
PH	841	836	827	818	810
BPDM	810	798	791	784	779
TFP	835	825	817	810	801

* Vs standard hydrogen electrode.

sulphuric acid concentration. PCPM does not give stable potentials either in sulphuric acid or hydrochloric acid medium. However, it gives stable transition potentials in acetic acid medium 90s after the addition of the last drop of cerium(IV) sulphate which marks the end-point. The transition potentials of PCPM are found to be 810, 804, 797, 794 and 788 ± 5 mV at 28° in 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5M acetic acid media respectively.

PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP do not give sharp end-points in the titration of 0.1-0.01N iron(II) with cerium(IV) sulphate in sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid or acetic acid medium because of the slow reduction of the coloured oxidised form of the indicator. However, they give very sharp end-points in the presence of phosphoric acid which catalyses the reduction of the oxidized indicator by iron(II). Phosphoric acid lowers the equivalence potential by lowering the formal potentials of cerium(IV)-cerium(III) and iron(III)-iron(II) couples by complexing with cerium(IV) and iron(III). It brightens the end-point and increases the stability of the end-point colour.

PH, BPDM and TFP give a sharp colour change from colourless to pink (orange red for TFP) in 0.5-1.75M sulphuric acid, 0.25-1.5M hydrochloric acid or 0.5-3M acetic acid solution containing 3-6 ml of 10M phosphoric acid and PCPM from colourless to pink in 0.5-1M sulphuric acid, 0.25-1M hydrochloric acid or 0.5-2M acetic acid in the presence of 3-6 ml of 10M phosphoric acid in a total volume of 60 ml. Sluggish end-points are obtained in lower concentrations of phosphoric acid

TABLE 2—CERIMETRIC DETERMINATION WITH PH, PCPM, BPDM AND TFP INDICATORS

Reductant taken (mg)	Indicators	Medium	Normality of Ce(SO ₄) ₂ (mg)	Reductant determined (mg)	Standard deviation (mg)	Colour change at the end-point
Iron(II)						
115.52	PH, BPDM and TFP	3-6 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5 - 1.75M H ₂ SO ₄ /0.25 - 1.5M HCl/0.5 - 3M HAc	0.1	115.53	0.093	Colourless to pink (Orange-red for TFP)
80.12		-do-	0.05	80.12	0.102	-do-
5.66		-do-	0.01	5.69	0.016	-do-
115.52	PCPM	3-6 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5 - 1M H ₂ SO ₄ /0.25 - 1M HCl/0.5 - 2M HAc	0.1	115.54	0.192	-do-
80.12		-do-	0.05	80.11	0.107	-do-
5.66		-do-	0.01	5.68	0.019	-do-
Molybdenum(V)						
193.98	PH, PCPM BPDM and TFP	1-3 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.2 - 1M H ₂ SO ₄ /1 - 2M HCl/0.2 - 3M HAc	0.1	194.01	0.266	-do-
96.69		-do-	0.05	96.75	0.124	-do-
9.73		-do-	0.01	9.77	0.025	-do-
Uranium(IV)						
120.30	PH	2-5 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.7 - 1.5M H ₂ SO ₄	0.05	120.20	0.152	Light-yellow to orange-red
11.34		-do-	0.01	11.40	0.044	-do-
120.30	BPDM	2-5 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.7 - 1M H ₂ SO ₄	0.05	120.19	0.075	-do-
11.34		-do-	0.01	11.40	0.037	-do-
Hydroquinone						
112.86	PH	2-5 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5 - 1.2M H ₂ SO ₄ /0.5 - 1M HCl or HAc	0.1	112.86	0.078	-do-
63.42		-do-	0.05	63.39	0.168	-do-
4.98		-do-	0.01	5.00	0.004	-do-
112.86	PCPM	2-5 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5 - 1.2M H ₂ SO ₄ /0.5 - 0.6M HCl/0.5 - 2M HAc	0.1	112.84	0.098	Light yellow to orange-red
63.42		-do-	0.05	63.43	0.138	-do-
4.98		-do-	0.01	4.97	0.008	-do-
112.86	BPDM and TFP	2-5 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5 - 1.2M H ₂ SO ₄ /0.5 - 1M HCl/0.5 - 2M HAc	0.1	112.76	0.102	-do-
63.43		-do-	0.05	63.44	0.094	-do-
4.98		-do-	0.01	5.00	0.029	-do-
Metol						
165.42	PH, BPDM and TFP	3-6 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5 - 1M H ₂ SO ₄ /0.2 - 0.5M HCl/0.3 - 3M HAc	0.1	165.73	0.160	-do-
87.51		-do-	0.05	87.37	0.121	-do-
12.85		-do-	0.01	12.90	0.039	-do-
Ascorbic Acid						
166.16	PH, BPDM and TFP	0.25 - 0.4M H ₂ SO ₄	0.1	166.06	0.177	Colourless to pink (orange-red for TFP)
80.26		-do-	0.05	80.18	0.137	-do-
166.16	PCPM	2-4 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5 - 1M H ₂ SO ₄	0.1	166.27	0.383	-do-
80.26		-do-	0.05	80.31	0.071	-do-
166.16	PH and PCPM	2-3 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.5 - 1M HCl	0.1	166.08	0.160	-do-
80.26		-do-	0.05	80.31	0.224	-do-
166.16	BPDM and TFP	2-3 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 0.8 - 1.2M HCl	0.1	166.06	0.177	-do-
80.26		-do-	0.05	80.18	0.143	-do-
166.16	PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP	2-6 ml of 10M H ₃ PO ₄ + 1 - 2M HAc	0.1	166.08	0.182	-do-
80.26		-do-	0.05	80.18	0.143	-do-
163.80	PH, PCPM	2-4M H ₃ PO ₄ (1-2M for PCPM)	0.1	163.69	0.225	-do-
80.29		-do-	0.05	80.29	0.100	-do-
8.43	TFP	-do-	0.01	8.45	0.015	-do-
4.12		-do-	0.005	4.13	0.010	-do-
1.00	PCPM	1-2M H ₃ PO ₄	0.002	1.00	0.005	-do-

acid (ii) they have smaller indicator correction and (iii) they function at lower acidities.

Titration of 0.05-0.01N uranium(IV) solution : In the titration of 0.05-0.01N uranium(IV) with cerium(IV) sulphate, only PH and BPDM function in sulphuric acid medium in the presence of phosphoric acid which sharpens and brightens the

end-point. The reaction between uranium(IV) and cerium(IV) sulphate induces the reaction between the oxidised indicator and uranium(IV) in the presence of phosphoric acid. PH gives sharp end-points from light yellow to orange-red in 0.7-1.5M sulphuric acid and BPDM from light yellow to orange-red in 0.7-1M sulphuric acid solution

containing 2-5 ml of 10M phosphoric acid in a total volume of 120 ml. At acidities lower than 0.7M precipitation occurs. Premature end-points are obtained with higher concentration of sulphuric acid. The stability of the end-point colour increases with decreasing concentration of uranium(IV) and sulphuric acid. The end-point colours of PH and BPDm are stable respectively for 6-13 and 3-7 min in 0.7M sulphuric acid and 3-8 and 2-6 min in 1.5M sulphuric acid.

It was found that 0.8-1.5 ml of 0.1% PH or BPDm solution is necessary in a total volume of 120 ml for proper indicator action. Higher concentrations of the indicator give premature end-points. The average indicator correction is 0.05 ml of 0.01N cerium(IV) sulphate solution.

PH and BPDm have advantages over ferroin in that they work at lower acidities and require less indicator correction. PH is a better indicator in this titration.

Titration of 0.1-0.01N hydroquinone : PH, PCPM, BPDm and TFP give sharp end-points from light yellow to orange-red in the titration of 0.1-0.01N hydroquinone with cerium(IV) sulphate in 0.5-1.2M sulphuric acid, 0.5-1M hydrochloric acid (0.5-6M for PCPM) or 0.5-2M acetic acid (0.5-1M for PH) solutions containing 2-5 ml of 10M phosphoric acid in a total volume of 60 ml. Higher concentrations of sulphuric and hydrochloric acids and lower concentrations of phosphoric acid give sluggish end-points. Premature end-points are obtained at higher acidities of phosphoric acid and higher titre values are got in higher concentrations of acetic acid. The end-point colour of PH, PCPM, BPDm and TFP in sulphuric and hydrochloric acid and acetic acid media is stable for about 6, 10, 5 and 5 min respectively.

A 0.8-3 ml of 0.1% PH, PCPM, BPDm or TFP is necessary for proper indicator action in a total volume of 60 ml. Higher concentrations of the indicator cause higher titre values. The average indicator correction required in this titration has been found to be 0.04 ml of 0.01N cerium(IV) sulphate for 1 ml of 0.1% indicator solution. PH is the most sensitive indicator in this titration.

Titration of 0.1-0.01N metol solution : Copper phthalocyanine tetrasulphonic acid¹² is the only indicator recommended for the cerimetric titration of metol. This indicator gives only a pink flash at the equivalence point. We have now developed PH, BPDm and TFP as excellent reversible indicators in this titration. The indicators give sharp end-points in the titration of 0.1-0.01N metol in 0.5-1M sulphuric acid, 0.2-0.5M hydrochloric acid or 0.3-3M acetic acid solution containing 3-6 ml of 10M phosphoric acid in a total volume of 60 ml. The behaviour of the indicators at lower and higher acidities is similar to that in the titration of hydroquinone. The orange-red colour is stable for about 10 s in sulphuric acid or acetic acid and 50-60 s in hydrochloric acid medium. The amount of indicator required and the indicator correction are

the same as those required in the titration of hydroquinone. Of the three indicators considered, TFP is the most sensitive in this titration.

Titration of ascorbic acid solution : Ferroin¹³, barium diphenylamine sulphonate (DS)¹³, N-phenyl anthranilic acid (NPA)¹³ and rhodamine 6G (Rh)¹³ were proposed as indicators in the titration of 0.1N ascorbic acid with cerium(IV) sulphate in 0.75-1.5M sulphuric acid solution containing 1 ml of syrupy phosphoric acid. Rh imparts in day light a greenish fluorescence which is sharply quenched by a slight excess of cerium(IV) sulphate. With ferroin, cerium(IV) sulphate should be added in fraction of a drop with the aid of a thin glass rod near the end-point. We have found that DS and NPA give variable results depending on the concentrations of the indicator.

PH, BPDm and TFP give very sharp end-points in 0.25-0.4M sulphuric acid solution, if they are added near the end of the titration. The end-point colour is stable for about 30 min. Higher concentration of acid give premature end-points. PCPM gives sharp colour change from colourless to pink at the end-point in 0.5-1M sulphuric acid solution containing 2-4 ml of 10M phosphoric acid. An increase in the acid concentration decreases the intensity and stability of the end-point colour. Thus the stability of the pink colour is 60 min in 0.5M sulphuric acid and 20 min in 1M sulphuric acid. Higher concentrations of sulphuric and phosphoric acids lead to premature end-points and to the destruction of the indicator. At lower acidities of phosphoric acid sluggish end-points are obtained.

PH and PCPM give sharp and correct end-points in 1-2M hydrochloric acid and BPDm and TFP in 0.8-1.2M hydrochloric acid in the presence of 2-3 ml of 10M phosphoric acid. No end-points are obtained with more than 2M hydrochloric acid. The pink colour of PH, PCPM, BPDm and TFP is stable for about 25, 20, 1 and 3 min respectively.

All the four indicators give sharp colour change from colourless to pink or orange-red at the equivalence point in 1-2M acetic acid solution containing 2-6 ml of 10M phosphoric acid. The end-point colour of the indicator is stable for about 20 min. Precipitation occurs if the concentration of acetic acid is more than 2M and less than 1M. In hydrochloric acid and acetic acid media lower concentrations of phosphoric acid give sluggish end-points and higher concentrations cause premature end-points.

The titration of ascorbic acid in phosphoric acid medium has certain advantages¹¹. Macro and micro amounts of ascorbic acid can be titrated with 0.1-0.005N cerium(IV) sulphate in 2-4M phosphoric acid using PH, BPDm and TFP indicators. The end-point colour of PH, BPDm and TFP is stable for 35, 25 and 20 min respectively. PCPM gives sharp and correct end-point in the titration of ascorbic acid with 0.1-0.002N cerium(IV) sulphate in 1-2M phosphoric acid solution. The pink colour of

PCPM is stable for 50 min. Premature end-points are obtained at lower acidities and overshoot end-points at higher acidities.

In the titration of 0.1-0.01N ascorbic acid atleast 2-3, 1-2.5, 0.8-2 and 0.8-2 ml of 0.1% PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP are necessary in sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid, acetic acid and phosphoric acid respectively for proper indicator action in a total volume of 60 ml. In the titration of ascorbic acid with 0.002N cerium(IV) sulphate, 0.4-0.7 ml of 0.1% of the indicator solution is necessary for proper indicator action in a total volume of 20 ml. Higher concentrations of the indicator cause over titration.

Citric, tartaric, succinic, acetic and malic acids, glucose, fructose, sucrose and starch do not interfere in the determination of a tenth of their amount of ascorbic acid. Oxalic acid does not interfere only in phosphoric acid medium. The results compare favourably with those obtained by the iodate method¹⁴. The sharpness of the end-points is in the order PCPM > PH > BPDM > TFP.

Comparison with other indicators : All four indicators have advantages over NPA and DS in that (i) they give sharper end-points, (ii) they function in sulphuric, hydrochloric, acetic and phosphoric acid media while NPA, DS and Rh function only in sulphuric acid medium and (iii) they have less indicator correction. They are superior to ferroin because (i) they work in lower concentrations of phosphoric acid, (ii) they function in hydrochloric and acetic acid media, (iii) they have smaller indicator correction and give sharper end-points and (iv) micro amounts of ascorbic acid can accurately be determined.

Determination of ascorbic acid in citrus fruit juices : Ascorbic acid present in citrus fruit juices was determined by a number of chemical methods¹⁵⁻²¹ in which no internal redox indicator was used. 2,6 Dichlorophenol indophenol¹⁵ is widely used for the determination of ascorbic acid in biological materials. But the reagent has several disadvantages. For example (i) the old samples of the reagent have low solubility in water, (ii) it gives poor end-points and (iii) its solution requires frequent standardisation and should be stored in a brown bottle in a refrigerator. We have now developed PH, PCPM, BPDM and TFP indicators in the cerimetric determination of ascorbic acid in citrus fruits.

Three varieties of citrus fruits, lime, sweet orange and sweet lime were selected. The presence of foam in the juice sometimes causes difficulty in getting good end-points. Addition of a drop of ethanol is found to break the foam. The proposed method does not have the limitations of the 2,6 dichlorophenol indophenol method and gives sharper end-points and reproducible results.

The results of the assay of vitamin 'C' tablets and injections in Table 4 compare favourably with those obtained by 2,6 dichlorophenol indophenol method.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF ASCORBIC ACID IN CITRUS FRUIT JUICES IN THE PRESENCE OF PH, PCPM, BPDM AND TFP INDICATORS

Fruit	Amount of ascorbic acid in 100 ml of fruit juice				
	2,6 dichlorophenol indophenol method (mg)	PH (mg)	PCPM (mg)	Cerium(IV) sulphate method using BPDM (mg)	TFP (mg)
<i>Lime Juice</i>					
Sample 1	38.2	38.9	39.6	38.9	38.9
2	32.8	32.4	33.1	32.4	32.4
3	34.9	34.4	34.6	34.4	34.4
4	30.6	30.3	30.4	30.9	31.3
<i>Sweet orange</i>					
Sample 1	41.6	41.4	41.8	41.1	41.0
2	43.2	43.6	43.4	43.9	44.1
3	40.8	40.6	40.6	40.2	41.1
4	40.2	40.4	40.4	40.6	40.8
<i>Sweet lime</i>					
Sample 1	38.4	38.3	38.4	38.5	39.5
2	46.1	46.4	46.3	46.7	46.7
3	41.9	41.7	41.9	41.8	41.8
4	43.6	43.6	43.6	43.7	43.9

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF ASCORBIC ACID IN VITAMIN C TABLETS AND INJECTIONS IN THE PRESENCE OF PH, PCPM, BPDM AND TFP

Tablet or injection	Quoted (mg)	Amount of ascorbic acid found by	
		2,6 dichlorophenol indophenol method (mg)	Cerium(IV) sulphate method ^a (mg)
<i>Tablets</i>			
Celin ^b	50	49.6	49.7
Celin ^b	100	99.3	99.2
Celin ^b	500	498.6	497.5
Suckce ^c	500	502.9	501.8
Chewce ^d	500	502.6	502.4
<i>Injection</i>			
Vitamin C ^e	500	502.3	501.6
Calcium ^f -Sandoz 10% + Vitamin C	500	501.2	500.4

a : average of six determinations ; Marketed by
 b : Glaxo Lab. (India) ; c : IDPL (India) ;
 d : Cyanamid (India) ; e : Harson Lab. (India) ;
 f : Sandoz (India).

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